

AN INSIGHT INTO THE COCRYSTALLIZATION OF POORLY SOLUBLE DRUG DIACEREIN

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Abstract

The goal of the present investigation utilizing cocrystallization to formulation and evaluation of Diacerein. To formulate and evaluate diacerein-loaded co-crystals, diacerein is combined with a different molecule (co-former) to generate a novel crystalline structure that may enhance its solubility, rate of dissolution, and bioavailability. Anti-solvent crystallization and solvent drop grinding are two techniques used to accomplish this. Following that, the co-crystals are analyzed using methods such as DSC, PXRD, FTIR, and SEM in order to verify their formation and assess their characteristics. A number of co-formers, including urea, tartaric acid, nicotinamide, and theophylline, can be combined with Diacerein, a weakly soluble drug used to treat osteoarthritis, to create co-crystals. The physicochemical properties of active pharmaceutical compounds are improved through cocrystallization using various approaches for the manufacturing of cocrystals, various solid and solution-based techniques can be used. The number of potential application where cocrystals can be used in combination with the development of cocrystals. Recently it has been proven that cocrystals provide desirable substitutes for flavor masking, improving mechanical properties, and developing and extending intellectual property, whereas previously solubility modification was thought to be the primary cause of cocrystal formation. More study on cocrystals production methods has become necessary as a result of the increased commercialization of cocrystals, with a focus on innovative methods that could offer efficient and environmentally appealing alternatives. This article reviews Diacerein cocrystal production methods and evaluation to use the unique physical property adjustability that cocrystal provide, with an emphasis on new development in various fields.

Keywords: Co-crystal, Diacerein, Cocrystallization, Formulation, Evaluation, Solvents.

1. Introduction:

Diacerein is an anti-inflammatory medication that is employed to treat osteoarthritis. Its limited solubility, dissolving rate, and other physicochemical characteristics make it a BCS class II drug. A drug's bulk and physicochemical qualities, which include chemical stability and flowability, can be influenced by its internal structure and crystal habit. Diacerein, 4,5-diacetoxy-9,10-dioxo-9,10-dihydro-anthracene-2-carboxylic acid belongs to class of anthraquinone that has been shown in experimental models to have anti-inflammatory effects. It has been demonstrated that diacerein inhibits the production and function of proinflammatory cytokines. Even though diacerein has been sold commercially in solid form as oral tablets for a long time, there is currently a dearth of trustworthy crystallographic data on the substance. When compiling drug master files, this is a disadvantage. Detailed structural information is very helpful when dealing with the common and frustrating issue of medication polymorphism in the solid state. According to this perspective, the final evaluation of the true form of the solid substance under investigation is provided by the combination of single-crystal and powder diffraction data, where available. (1)

While crystals are characterized by the repeating spacing of constituent atoms or molecules in a three-dimensional array, amorphous forms have atoms or molecules distributed randomly, as in a liquid. The spontaneous grouping of particles into a repeating ordered array, or regular geometric pattern, is known as crystallization. (2) A cocrystal is a homogeneous, multicomponent crystalline structure where all of the constituents are present in specific stoichiometric quantities and are stabilized and kept together by non-covalent interactions. Pharmaceutical cocrystals are crystalline solids made up of two or more distinct molecules, usually cocrystal formers (also known as "coformers") and (API), in the same crystal lattice. Cocrystallization is an innovative method that provides a widely used and promising alternative method to customize the solubility, intrinsic dissolution rate, and therefore, bioavailability of APIs. (3).

Figure 1: Steps in the Cocystal Formation Process.

A novel and emerging method for creating pharmaceutical products with enhanced mechanical and physicochemical qualities is crystal engineering and crystallization. To improve an API's characteristics, crystal engineering methods comprise the production of very fine particles, high energy amorphous forms, metastable polymorphs and co-crystals.

(4)

- In comparison to alternative solid forms like amorphous solids and solid solutions, crystalline forms are greatly favoured since they are typically more stable, repeatable, and purifiable.
- Different crystal forms have varying rates of dissolution and inherent solubility, which can significantly affect bioavailability.
- Crystal packing plays a critical role in temperature and humidity stability. The unpredictable nature of crystal structures and physical characteristics makes it difficult to obtain and maintain patent protection for an API due to legal concerns. (5)

The therapeutic efficacy and production cost of solid dosage forms are significantly influenced by the physicochemical properties of active pharmaceutical ingredients (APIs), including their

stability, particle size, powder flowability, taste, hygroscopicity, solubility, and compatibility. In oral medication delivery systems, the solubility and rate of drug molecule dissolution have a major impact on gastrointestinal absorption. However, the (BCS) II and IV classes, which comprise 40% of currently marketed medications and 90% of new chemical entities, suffer from low bioavailability and poor water solubility, which have a significant impact on drug product performance. (6) It is widely accepted that the characteristics of a particular crystalline substance are directly influenced by the arrangement of atoms in the unit cell and crystal lattice. Thus, by adjusting the crystal packing configurations, it is possible to change the physicochemical characteristics of solid drug forms. (7) For example, only molecules with the right ionizable groups may form salts, and hydrates and solvates are frequently unstable due to the tendency of water and solvent molecules to lose their properties over time. In contrast, every API has the potential to form cocrystals with the right coformer, regardless of whether it is acidic, basic, or nonionized. Because they may change the crystal structure of APIs without changing their pharmacological character, pharmaceutical cocrystals have garnered a lot of interest from the pharmaceutical industry and academics over the past 20 years. Cocrystals are a well-known yet relatively new molecular entity. Over the last 10 years, these new solids have shown an abundance of promise in altering the pharmacokinetic and physicochemical characteristics of medications. (8) Several medications are unable to enter the market due to poor bioavailability and solubility in watery environments. Co-crystallization is one method for increasing the solubility of pharmaceuticals that are weakly water soluble. Co-crystals are solid crystalline compounds made up of two or more chemicals in a stoichiometric ratio, with one being an (API) and the other a co-former. Intermolecular interactions allow the API and co-former to combine in a co-crystal. (9)

2. Various Methods of Cocrystal preparation/formulation of Diacerein:

Diacerein can be synthesized efficiently in a limited number of steps from the naturally occurring glucopyranoside aloin. The two main categories of cocrystal manufacturing methods are solution-based and solid-state. Solution-based procedures are production approaches that use a significant excessive amount of solvent requiring a later isolation stage to separate the crystalline product from the mother liquor. Solid-state methods, on the other hand, use very little or no solvent.

2.1. Solid State Methods.

2.1.1. Contact Formation method:

It has been observed that cocrystals develop spontaneously when pure API and coformer are mixed under regulated air conditions. Cocrystallization is carried out without the use of mechanical forces. However, in certain situations, pure components were briefly ground before being mixed. Rodriguez-Hornedo et al. studied how the premilling of starting materials affected the rates of cocrystallization of carbamazepine and nicotinamide, hence this demonstrated that premilled reactants cocrystallized much quicker than unmilled reactants (12 vs 80 days, respectively). Also, independent of mechanical activation, greater cocrystallization rates have been observed for the same system at higher temperatures and relative humidity.

(10)

2.1.2. Solid State Grinding method:

Solid state grinding procedures have been successfully employed to produce cocrystal powder samples. Two styles are used: (dry) grinding and liquid-assisted grinding. Dry grinding is the process of combining the target molecule and coformer in dry solid form using pressure, either manually (mortar and pestle) or mechanically (automatic ball mill). Dry grinding differs from melt crystallization in that the solid starting ingredients are not intended to melt while grinding. To ensure consistency, the temperature reached during grinding is frequently measured and noted. Two sulphathiazole:carboxylic acid cocrystals were formed by grinding stoichiometric equivalents of sulphathiazole with the appropriate carboxylic acid for 90 minutes in a Retsch mixer mill at 25 Hz with the temperature not allowed to exceed 37 °C.(11).

Solid state grinding is more efficient than solution-based techniques in that it does not lose yield to the solvent due to solubility. (12)

2.1.3. Extrusion method:

Twin Screw Extrusion (TSE) and Hot Melt Extrusion (HME), occurs at temperatures below the melting point of either starting material and is carried out in a separate piece of equipment—an aptly titled twin screw extruder. This equipment features a single barrel with two co-/counter-rotating screws. Material can be mixed and moved simultaneously down the barrel's length thanks to screw action. Daurio et al. developed four model cocrystals utilizing a 16 mm twin screw extruder with four temperature zones that could be controlled. (13)

2.1.4. Hot Melt Extrusion method:

Hot melt extrusion method (HME) is a new component to the cocrystal preparation process. This specialized approach employs a heated screw extruder to melt and mix the target molecule and coformer simultaneously. Typically, the initial components are combined in a specific molar ratio and fed into the heated extruder. Melting happens, allowing for intimate mixing of the beginning ingredients. Cocrystals form directly in the melt, and pure cocrystal extrudate is continually segregated from the extruder. The approach has several advantages, including the elimination of organic solvents, quick working periods, higher conversion compared to solution-based procedures, reduced waste, and the technology's suitability for continuous pharmaceutical processing. Moradiya et al. investigated the synthesis of cocrystals of carbamazepine-cinnamic acid utilizing a twin-screw and single screw extruder. (14)

2.1.5. High Shear Wet Granulation method:

High shear wet granulation method, which is commonly used in therapeutic product formulation, has been examined as a method of producing cocrystals. This approach involves the aggregation of powder particles in a liquid medium with the addition of a binder. Technically, the technique is carried out in a high shear granulator, which applies shear to the powder combination using impellers and choppers. The mechanism of cocrystal formation by high shear granulation is not fully understood, however it is thought to be analogous to liquid assisted grinding or slurry transformation. Granules comprising a 1:1 piracetam:tartaric acid cocrystal were effectively generated from a mixture of piracetam, tartaric acid, and a range of excipients in the presence of water using a Bohle micro granulator. (15)

2.2. Solution Based Methods:

Cocrystallization from solution can be accomplished using a variety of methods, which will be explained in the next section. First, investigate some universal solution crystallization notions. The discrepancy between the claimed solubility concentration at that temperature in that solvent and the actual experimental concentration is known as supersaturation, and it is the driving force behind crystallization. There are two concentrations to take into account in a cocrystal system: the coformer and the target molecule. The supersaturation for cocrystallization is determined by the concentrations of both in relation to the solubility of the cocrystal, which is best expressed in terms of the target molecule and conformer. (16)

2.2.1. Evaporative Cocrystallization method:

Evaporative cocrystallization is a common method of producing cocrystals, usually used to produce single crystal cocrystals appropriate for diffraction investigations to elucidate cocrystal structure. The approach comprises the nucleation and development of a cocrystal from a solution of both coformers in a solvent, with supersaturation given by evaporating the solvent from the solution. Individual cocrystals or the bulk crystal sample should be collected before the solution evaporates completely to ensure the recovery of a clean crystal(s). A slow rate of evaporation is often preferred to ensure the development of fewer bigger crystals rather than a large number of smaller crystals. (17)

2.2.2. Cooling Crystallization method:

In order to make a scalable solution cocrystallization approach, carbamazepine:nicotinamide cocrystals were prepared from ethanol using a developed seeded cooling crystallization. Solvent selection, determination of the thermodynamically stable cocrystal working range, and desupersaturation kinetics were all taken into account while designing the process. (18).

2.2.3. Reaction Cocrystallization method:

By mixing separate feed solutions of either of the starting ingredients, cocrystals of carbamazepine:saccharin were created by reaction cocrystallization. The ternary phase diagram served as the basis for the technique, which showed a stable working range for cocrystal formation and the anticipated correlation between supersaturation and induction time. Under ambient circumstances, reaction cocrystallization was also used to form a carbamazepine:nicotinamide cocrystal. (19)

2.2.4. Isothermal Slurry Conversion method:

Using this method, the target molecule and coformer are suspended in a solvent, typically in a predetermined molar ratio, with the solid fraction always remaining in excess. Practically speaking, the method may also be used by including the target molecule into a solvent-based coformer solution or suspension. The creation of a clear (completely dissolved) starting solution is not necessary for this solution-based technique. (20)

2.3. Supercritical Fluid Methods:

Three unique methods that concentrate on various supercritical CO₂ properties—solvent, antisolvent, and atomization enhancement—have been used to effectively generate cocrystals utilizing supercritical fluid technology, mainly with the use of supercritical carbon dioxide (CO₂). (21)

2.3.1. Cocrystallization with Supercritical Solvent method:

The Cocrystallization with Supercritical Solvent (CSS) method eliminates the need for hazardous organic solvents by suspending the API and coformer as a slurry in liquid or supercritical CO₂ using the solvent power of supercritical CO₂. (22)

2.3.2. Rapid Expansion of Supercritical Solvents method (RESS):

The Rapid Expansion of Supercritical Solvents (RESS) method involves depressurizing the CO₂ phase through a nozzle into a drying chamber at atmospheric pressure after the supercritical fluid (supercritical CO₂) has been saturated with a solid substrate (API and coformer in the case of producing cocrystals). Using this method, Müllers et al. created ibuprofen-nicotinamide cocrystal microparticles. (23)

2.3.3. Supercritical Antisolvent Cocrystallization method:

The idea behind using supercritical CO₂ as an antisolvent for cocrystallization is that the coformer and API become less soluble in supercritical CO₂, which enables them to precipitate together in a cocrystalline structure. This method may allow for the control of the cocrystals or API's polymorphic form. (24)

2.3.4. Supercritical CO₂-Assisted Spray Drying

The idea behind using supercritical CO₂ as an atomization enhancer is that when depressurized concurrently with liquid solutions, supercritical fluids can improve the breakdown of liquid jets into small droplets. Using a nozzle that contains supercritical CO₂, a solution comprising the dissolved initial cocrystal components is sprayed into a drying chamber at atmospheric pressure in a single step. In order to create micro- to nanosized theophylline cocrystals with several cofomers and optimize the cocrystal particles' shape and dissolving characteristics, Padrela et al. employed the Supercritical Enhanced Atomization technology. (25)

Dry grinding at a set frequency and duration	Solid state methods
Grinding with liquid assistance for a predetermined amount of time and frequency.	
Extrusion method	
Hot melt extrusion method	
High shear wet granulation method	
Isothermal slurry conversion method	Solution Based Methods
Evaporative cocrystallization	
Assisted evaporative cocrystallization	
Spray drying method	
Reactive cocrystallization method	
Cooling cocrystallization method	
Antisolvent cocrystallization	Supercritical fluid methods
Cocrystallization with supercritical solvent, or Supercritical antisolvent cocrystallization.	
Supercritical assisted spray drying	

Table 1. Standard methods for preparation of cocrystals

2.4. Miscellaneous Cocrystal Preparation:

2.4.1. Laser Irradiation method:

This technique involves irradiating powder mixes of cocrystal formers with a high-power CO₂ laser to cause them to recrystallize into a cocrystal structure. This method has been employed by Titapiwatanakun et al. to make caffeine cocrystals using malonic and oxalic acids. (26)

2.4.2. Electrochemically Induced Cocrystallization method:

Urbanus et al. showed how cocrystallization and electrochemistry may be used to remove carboxylic acid products in situ. (27)

2.4.3. Resonant Acoustic Mixing method:

The target molecule and coformer have been combined in the presence of a liquid using resonant acoustic mixing to generate a cocrystal without the use of any grinding media hence, this technique encourages close mixing of the ingredients by transferring mechanical energy acoustically into a wet powder combination. (28)

2.4.4. Spray Drying method:

For converting liquids (solutions, suspensions, and slurries) into solid powders, spray drying is a continuous, one-step procedure. It is advantageous since it is a continuous, highly controlled, and rapid process. Because of its quick solidification, spray drying has been used extensively to create amorphous solid dispersions, but it has also been utilized to create cocrystals. (29)

2.4.5. Freeze-Drying

Lyophilization, the technical term for freeze-drying, has been used primarily as a processing method to preserve a wide range of goods, including food and medications. The substance is first frozen, and the surrounding pressure is then decreased to enable the frozen water in the material to sublime straight from the solid to the gas phase. Recent studies have also shown that it is a viable technique for creating novel solid forms of cocrystal systems. (30)

2.4.6. Electrospray Technology method:

Using an electric field to simultaneously create and charge droplets is known as electrospraying. In this procedure,

As a solution containing the dissolved chemicals exits a capillary nozzle maintained at high potential, an electric field elongates the solution droplets to form a jet. After the solution jet has dried, the generated particles are collected on a charged powder collector. Patil et al. showed how this method may produce carbamazepine and itraconazole cocrystals with various coformers. (31)

3. Different Evaluation Methods of Diacerein Co-crystals:

3.1 DSC (Differential Scanning Calorimetry):

Every co-crystal of Diacerein can be made using the solvent drop grinding procedure had the distinctive endothermic peak of diacerein. When the co-crystal exhibits varying melting points,

DSC is typically used to display the co-crystal composition of pharmaceutical powders. The following illustrates the temperature behavior of co-crystals and commercial diacerein. Diacerein occurred on a steep endothermic peak at around 236.0°C, which corresponds to its melting point, according to the DSC curve. However, the endothermic peak shifted towards a lower temperature at 133.6°C and 170.2°C, respectively, in the co-crystals that were produced using urea and tartaric acid as cofomers. A shift in the endothermic peak toward a lower temperature signifies a drop in the drug's melting point in co-crystals. The drug's enhanced solubility can be attributed to its lower melting point.

3.2 Powder X-ray diffraction:

Using an X-ray diffractometer, the X-ray diffraction pattern of several co-crystals was examined. When compared to different co-crystals, the pure drug's X-ray diffraction pattern exhibits more peaks. The drug-tartaric acid co-crystal's XRD spectra showed an increase in intensity but a decrease in the number of peaks. The intensity of the peaks in the drug-urea co-crystal's XRD spectra has increased. There were significant diffraction peaks at $2\theta=15843$ and 16673 . It appears that particles crystallized using the solvent drop co-grinding method in the presence of co-coformer did not undergo structural modification because In the presence of co-crystal cofomer, the XRD spectra of the pure drug and cocrystals had substantially identical diffraction patterns (2θ values). However, variations in the sample's crystal size and behavior, which may be related to the drug's varying solubility in the media, could account for the variations in the relative intensities of their peaks. (32).

3.3 Fourier Transform Infrared (FT-IR) Spectroscopy:

The FTIR spectrum of the diacerein standard, crystallized from THF, was reported for the 2000–700 cm^{-1} region. The reflectance mode was used for FT-IR analyses in order to prevent nujol interference and any changes that might occur from grinding the material. With the exception of the C-O-C peak resolution (1207 and 1190 cm^{-1} by HATR vs. 1208 cm^{-1} by nujol), comparative analysis of the FT-IR spectra in this instance did not uncover any notable alterations carried on by excessive grinding. (33).

3.4 Scanning Electron Microscopy (SEM):

SEM was used to evaluate the produced crystal's surface characteristics. Prior to analysis, powder samples had been coated with a thin layer of gold at 10 Torr vacuum and mounted onto an aluminum stub using double-sided adhesive tape. An electron beam with an acceleration

potential of 20 kV was used to scan the specimens, and secondary electron mode pictures were obtained. (34)

3.5 Physicochemical properties of cocrystals:

3.5.1: Physical stability:

A change in a substance's state that is not comparable with a change in the chemical composition is referred to as a physical change. Hardness, plasticity, elasticity, hygroscopicity, solubility, and melting point are some of the physical characteristics of solid-state materials. One effective method for enhancing the physical characteristics and preserving the physical stability of medicinal compounds is cocrystallization. It could undergo undesirable physical changes while being manufactured and stored. Only the melting point and hygroscopicity will be covered in this part; other characteristics will be covered in the sections that follows below. (35)

3.5.1.1 Melting points:

Solid drug forms allow manufacturers a practical means of drug identification, purification, storage, and transportation. Compared to liquid forms, solid forms are easier for patients to transport and administer. However, because of their low melting points, several medications are liquid at room temperature. By adding an appropriate cofomer to the crystalline lattices, cocrystallization can change the melting point of liquid medications. To create and sustain drowsiness and general anesthesia, propofol is administered. Because of its low melting point (18 °C), it is made as an oil-in-water emulsion, which leads to related issues such instability, injection discomfort, and hyperlipidemia. (36)

3.5.1.2 Hygroscopicity:

The hygroscopicity of a medicinal substance should be closely considered as it may impact its physicochemical properties, such as its solubility, rate of dissolution, stability, bioavailability, and mechanical qualities. For ex: Dasatinib anhydrate, for instance, was more soluble than the monohydrate version. (37) Thus, one of the key difficulties in medication development is preserving the anhydrate form's hygroscopic stability. To address this issue, a number of approaches have been used, such as coating the medicinal product with enteric polymers, using suitable packaging to minimize moisture absorption, or inserting suitable excipients in the

formulation. In fact, cocrystal formation has been shown in several investigations to enhance the hygroscopic stability of medications. (38).

3.5.2 Chemical stability:

The production of a stable pharmaceutical formulation is complicated by the tendency for chemical degradation of medication ingredients to happen throughout the production and storage phases. Developing a successful plan to reduce or remove medication degradants is essential. Pharmaceutical cocrystals have recently surfaced as a potential solution to address APIs' chemical instability in the solid form. (39) The area in the crystal structure following to the reaction groups is known as the reaction cavity. High likelihood of solid state chemical formation and molecular mobility are caused by a wide reaction cavity. Following exposure to ambient light irradiation, epalrestat (EPR), a medication used to treat diabetic neuropathy, is prone to the photodegradation of isomerization (E,Z to Z,Z). (40)

3.5.3 Mechanical properties:

The mechanical characteristics of crystalline materials are essential for a number of solid dosage form manufacturing processes, including coating, blending, milling, granulation, and tableting. The mechanical deformation modes of solid materials include fragmentation, viscoelastic, plastic, and elastic. In general, superior compressibility—which is permanent and irreversible once tension is removed—can be seen in materials with better plasticity characteristics. However, a barrier to creating tablet formulations is the poor mechanical qualities of many organic substances. It has been shown that by changing the crystal packing, cocrystallization can significantly enhance the mechanical characteristics of medications. (41) (42) Additionally, Mishra et al. conducted nanoindentation to examine the mechanical characteristics of caffeine-glutaric acid cocrystals on various crystalline faces. They discovered that the strength of the intermolecular connections in the crystal structure with regard to the direction of indentation and the number of potential slip planes influenced the anisotropic polymorphs. Hard materials are produced by form II's strong intermolecular contacts, increased interlayer energy, and absence of easy slip planes. Form I was soft due to weaker intermolecular interactions and more easy slip planes. (43)

3.5.4 Optical properties:

Optical characteristics of drugs may have practical uses in biomedicine. Drugs with high fluorescence, for instance, can be employed as biocompatible probes for lipid droplet imaging

in tissue slices and cells as well as bioimaging. The optical characteristics of solid materials are often influenced by the arrangement of crystals, molecule stacking, and intermolecular interactions. Recently, it has been shown that cocrystal engineering can change the optical properties of drugs. The following examples demonstrate how adding cofomers to crystal lattices can alter the optical properties of medications. (44). A naturally occurring pigment, emodin (EM) has a number of pharmacological properties, including anti-inflammatory, cathartic, anti-cancer, and antioxidative properties. Through cocrystallization with a number of colorless cofomers, the color of EM was adjusted from yellow to dark red. Li et al. contended that the color transition from yellow to red is influenced by charge-transfer interactions and $\pi \cdots \pi$. The maximum absorption wavelength may redshift as a result of the enhanced charge-transfer process from the excited state to the ground state caused by the greater $\pi \cdots \pi$ interactions. (45)

3.5.5 Bioavailability:

Bioavailability is the proportion of the medication that enters the bloodstream. The limited bioavailability of several therapeutic candidates caused them to fail during the preclinical phase of drug development. Cocrystallization has shown the ability to enhance the bioavailability and solubility of poorly water-soluble drugs, hence improving their in vivo performance over the past ten years. For medications that lack ionizable functional groups and so cannot form salts, this approach is particularly appropriate. (46) However, due to its relatively less solubility and bioavailability, APG has limited therapeutic utility. The bioavailability of the APG and 4,4'-bipyridine cocrystal was 3.9 times greater than that of the parent medication. (47) The dissolving steps of strongly soluble cocrystals may result in solution-mediated phase transition, whereby poorly soluble medicines precipitate throughout the solutions, reducing the cocrystals' solubility advantage. This issue indicates that the solubility and bioavailability of the medications are not always improved by cocrystallization. In order to increase the bioavailability of weakly water-soluble medications, it is necessary to postpone or stop the solution-mediated phase transformation process. (48).

3.6 Saturation Solubility Studies:

The saturation solubility investigations of Diacerein were performed out in distinctive oils such as corn oil, peanut oil, sesame oil, hydrogenated oil, soybean oil, solvents such as distilled water, Myglyol, Labrafil M 1944 CS, Oleic acid, Transcutol P, Labrafac lipophile WL 1349 (Consists of medium chain triglycerides of caprylic (C8) and capric (C10) acids), Geliol SC (Consists of a mixture of refined soybean oil, glyceryl distearate (C18) and polyglyceryl 3 dioleate (

C18:1)), Capryol 90 (propyleneglycol mono caprylate), Labrafac PG (PG Dicaprolate), Plurol Diisostearique (polyglyceryl -3-diostearate), Poly ethylene glycol 400 (PEG 400), Propylene glycol (PG), Glycerol and Span 80 in various buffers such as pH-6.8, phosphate-buffer, pH 1.2 phosphate buffer, and pH 7.4 phosphate buffer. An excess of the drug was added to 2 millilitres of each chosen vehicle to create saturated solutions, which were then shaken on a mechanical shaker for 48 hours at 25 degrees Celsius. Samples were gathered and centrifuged for 15 minutes at 10,000 rpm after achieving equilibrium. The amount of medication dissolved was measured using UV-visible spectrophotometry after 100 μ L of the supernatant was collected and appropriately diluted with methanol. For every solvent, solubility was measured three times. (49).

4. Conclusion:

Among the most promising methods for enhancing the physicochemical characteristics of API's is crystallisation. Cocrystals can be manufactured in a variety of ways, from standard lab-scale manufacturing techniques to possibly large-scale continuous manufacturing methods. Standard formulation and evaluation of both well established and recently developed cocrystal production methods are provided in this review. Furthermore, an in-depth comprehension of the potential mechanisms of crystallization in multiple methods is provided. As cocrystals continue to grow interest and prove their intrinsic value, the range of established cocrystal application areas are increasing globally. In conclusion, the pharmaceutical industry can use the cocrystallization technique to transform bioavailable and poorly compressible API's into forms that can be compressed directly. Diacerein-loaded cocrystals are a potentially effective formulation techniques for improving the biopharmaceutical profile of medications with low solubility. Pharmaceutical cocrystals have the potential to greatly enhance drug solubility, stability and therapeutic results when used with the right conformer, strong formulation techniques, and through characterization.

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